

Relationship between Export and Economic Growth in Pakistan by Using OLS technique

Author's Details:

- ⁽¹⁾**Qurab Ali**-Student of MS-Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur Mirs
⁽²⁾**Dr.Maria Shaikh**-Assistant Professor-IBA-University of Sindh Jamshoro
⁽³⁾**Dr.Aisha Bashir Shah**-Assistant Professor-IBA-University of Sindh Jamshoro
⁽⁴⁾**Dr.Faiz Muhammad Shaikh**-Associate Professor-SZABAC-Dokri-Sindh-Pakistan

Abstract

The current research investigates the Relationship between Export and Economic Growth in Pakistan by Using OLS technique. Data were collected from various secondary sources. Data is taken from 1990-2012 for Pakistan. Data for Real GDP, Real exports, Labor and Gross capital formation is taken from **World Development Indicator**. Here Gross capital formation is taken as proxy for Share of investment (SI) in GDP. Economist wants to achieve economic stability through different policies. As we want to explore the impact of exports on economy through trade policy, so we construct methodology and variable construction according to exports.

A time series data from 1990 to 2012 is used here. The result based on OLS technique suggests that there is positive relationship between exports and economic growth. But strong effect is from growth to exports and exports to economic growth has smaller role as suggested by empirical results. As theory suggests that outward oriented policies were adopted by many LDCs that lead to ELG and replaced inward or import substitution policies. But this study gives support to the idea that economic growth itself induces trade flows in Pakistan from 1990-2012.

Keywords: Export, Economic Growth, OLS technique

Introduction: Send out will be viewed as as an motor for monetary development of a country. A standout amongst the purposes behind the fast development of east asian nations may be their fantastic send out execution. What's more it will be because of usage of fare turned arrangements by A percentage for asian nations. Development in fares prompts expand in the incomes about Components of production, which thus builds the interest for enter for further extension clinched alongside generation. Those coming about weight around down home limit from claiming preparation might energize innovative unrest transform What's more venture chances. Fare execution will be a imperative apparatus of employment creation, change of offset for installment position, accelerated monetary development and expand the money level. What's more existing standard of the massenet. An and only such growths Might Additionally make diffused abroad through specialized foul aid. What's more help. The connection the middle of fares Also eco Growth might a chance to be unidirectional alternately bidirectional. 'Export headed Growth hypothesis' states that send out makes development. On taking after way. Firstly, fare advancement incentives and schemes improve fares to prepare that's only the tip of the iceberg products, which thus prompt specialization.

Send out may be recognized Similarly as a motor from claiming monetary development of a organizations in the nation. A standout amongst those purposes behind those fast development for east asian nations may be their phenomenal fare execution. Send out development need point of finer asset allocation, economies of scale formation. Also generation efficiency, capital formation, Also vocation era. Distinctive nations indicates distinctive result, Possibly bidirectional or unidirectional relationship for fares. Also budgetary development. An extensive numbers for experimental investigations in this zone need centered on the 'causal' association between fares. Furthermore budgetary development. Hundreds from claiming papers have been composed on the experimental association between fares. What's more development in the secret word two decades in distinctive nations.

For a standout amongst those investigations carried out Toward Quddus What's more Saeed (2005), it might have been investigated that higher rate of fares Growth prompts higher financial development by providing for An fitting channel i. E fare expands pay about element about preparation because of which request for figure about generation expands which thus expands innovative unrest transform Also speculation opportunities, which helps a greater amount handling Also additional fares which prompts monetary development. They utilized Granger causality test for time 1970-2004. Following this model it might have been discovered that sure relationship exist b/w fare Also monetary development.

Likewise Shirazi et. Al (2004) utilized co mix systems for Johansen (1988) What's more Johansen Also Juselius (1990) Also Granger causality test over those 1960 will 2003 period to figure out connection the middle of universal exchange Also Growth with those assistance of import substitution Furthermore fare advancement method to Pak. They found long run unidirectional relationship running from fares should financial development.

Mahmood an Akhtar (1996) likewise examined the same association for time period 1984-1993 Toward utilizing twenty two outside business sectors What's more merchandise arrangement of Pak fares. Those product creation impact might have been negative. It might have been not transformed considerably over those occasion when. Because of fast debasement Furthermore large amount of defilement Pak fares rose best insignificantly.

Khalid et. Al (2004) concentrated on the impact of conversion scale instability and fare Growth b/w Pak Also heading adrift profession accomplices for 1991 with 2004 by utilizing co mix Also error-correction systems Furthermore discovered that instability from claiming conversion scale need negative Also critical impacts to Pak, Australia, Newzealand,UK Furthermore us. It indicated long run impact for Australia, uk What's more singapore same time no connection might have been discovered for bangladesh What's more malaysia.

Previously, an additional contemplate Eventually Tom's perusing Mutairi (1993), he investigated that dependent upon upon what amount of Growth for fares help investment improvement. Granger causality test alongside propelled econometric strategies were used to inspect the qualities for time arrangement included. Information might have been taken for 1959-1991. Outcomes need indicated that over pakistan fares need not assumed the part of motor about development. So, lesquerella noteworthy part of fares in the improvement transform of pakistan is dependable for the discoveries for prior investigations for different nations.

Trade will be recognized Similarly as a impetus from claiming monetary development for a nation. Fares continuously those imperative and only profession are acknowledged Concerning illustration essential part about advancement for both Creating Furthermore created countries. A standout amongst those purposes behind those fast development for east asian nations is their phenomenal fare execution. Send out execution will be extremely critical apparatus from claiming vocation creation, change of equalization about installment position, accelerated financial development Also build the salary level Also existing standard of the dominant part.

Fares improve monetary development through separate channels/linkages.

1. Those development to fares increments incomes for elements from claiming handling. When pay increases, it builds the interest for inputs for further development On production, because of expand in buying force of the individuals. Those resultant weight ahead household limit enhances mechanical transformation transform Also speculation chances. This enhanced engineering organization Also more financing expands preparation. This thus expands vocation which brings about monetary development. Quddus and Saeed(2005)2. Fares Push delicate and tricky innovations (marketing, creation Furthermore administration expertise) Narayan Furthermore smith (2004) which increments profit for elements for processing (labor, capital) [Grossman Furthermore Helpman (1991); Kim (1998)]. An change On HC (human capital) prompts expansion fares. Likewise HC stock builds the nature from claiming workforce that enhances work profit Furthermore expands the processing of exportable merchandise that brings about budgetary development. 3. The remote trade earned starting with fares may be utilized for imports about capital What's more different middle of the road products which expand generation possibility done a nation which expands development. MacKinnon (1964) Also

Chenery What's more Strout (1966). 4. As stated by send out advancement technique (EP) fare development prompts better asset allotment and it makes economies about scale (Helpman Also Krugman, 1985) Also processing effectiveness (Bhagwati Furthermore Srinivasan, 1979; Krueger, 1980) through mechanical advancement (Grossman and Helpman, 1991), money formation, Furthermore employment era. This the sum prompts budgetary development. 5. Those nations on which fares Push specialization done high-technology; skill-intensive products that experience fast mechanical transformation advancement Also development at the liability for nations that practice Previously, low-technology merchandise. Youthful (1991).

Model:

This regression line is taken from Panayiotis et.al (2005) study.

$$RGDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 REX_t + \alpha_2 SI_t + \alpha_3 L_t + \mu_t$$

$$REX = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RGDP_t + \beta_2 SI_t + \beta_3 L_t + u_t$$

$$t = 1, 2, \dots, T$$

Where RGDP= real GDP

REX= real exports

SI= share of investment in GDP

L = number of persons employed.

U_t and μ_t = disturbance term.

For obvious reasons it is expected that SI_t and L_t are positively correlated with real GDP. On the other hand, Gylfason (1999) found that increases in the share of investment in GDP (SI_t) are associated with improvements in export performance.

3.2.2 Ordinary least square (OLS) technique:

OLS technique is used here to find relationship between exports and economic growth with the help of labor force and investment share in GDP. OLS is used because it is best technique which gives significant results.

3.2 Data and Variables:

3.2.1. Data Source:

Data is taken from 1990-2012 for Pakistan.

Data for Real GDP, Real exports, Labor and Gross capital formation is taken from **World Development Indicator**.

Here Gross capital formation is taken as proxy for Share of investment (SI) in GDP

3.3.2 Construction and trend of variables:

Economist wants to achieve economic stability through different policies. As we want to explore the impact of exports on economy through trade policy, so we construct methodology and variable construction according to exports.

A time series data from 1990 to 2012 is used here.

The following variables are taken to analyze the impact of exports on economic growth:

1. Real Gross domestic product (RGDP):

It measures economic growth in real terms. It is taken in constant 2005 US\$. The trend and descriptive statistics of economic growth in Pakistan from 1990-2012 is showed in Figure 1.

Eexports series:

Estimation Command:

ls lreexports c lreexports(-1)

Date: 12/28/13 Time: 22:41
 Sample: 1990 2012
 Included observations: 22

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
. * .	. * .	1	0.194	0.194	0.9461	0.331
. .	. * .	2	-0.049	-0.090	1.0090	0.604
. * .	. * .	3	0.076	0.109	1.1709	0.760
. * .	. * .	4	-0.085	-0.137	1.3853	0.847
. * .	. * .	5	-0.168	-0.114	2.2667	0.811
*** .	*** .	6	-0.403	-0.404	7.6368	0.266
. ** .	. * .	7	-0.199	-0.067	9.0289	0.251
. * .	. ** .	8	-0.151	-0.227	9.8842	0.273
. .	. .	9	-0.047	0.045	9.9745	0.353
. * .	. .	10	0.115	-0.007	10.558	0.393
. * .	. .	11	0.090	0.005	10.948	0.448
. * .	. * .	12	0.105	-0.138	11.536	0.484

Series is Stationary for exports at first difference.

Labor series:

Estimation Command:

ls llabor c llabor(-1)

Date: 12/28/13 Time: 22:58
 Sample: 1990 2012
 Included observations: 22

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
. * .	. * .	1	0.067	0.067	0.1127	0.737
. .	. .	2	0.006	0.001	0.1136	0.945
. .	. .	3	0.026	0.026	0.1330	0.988
. * .	. * .	4	-0.152	-0.156	0.8106	0.937
. * .	. * .	5	-0.086	-0.067	1.0416	0.959
. * .	. * .	6	0.070	0.083	1.2049	0.977
. .	. .	7	0.023	0.024	1.2228	0.990
. .	. * .	8	-0.049	-0.075	1.3145	0.995
. * .	. * .	9	0.094	0.076	1.6760	0.996
. * .	. * .	10	-0.163	-0.165	2.8491	0.985
. ** .	. ** .	11	-0.287	-0.263	6.7926	0.816
. .	. .	12	-0.029	-0.020	6.8385	0.868

Series is stationary for labor at first difference.

Gcap series:

Estimation Command:

ls lgcap c lgcap(-1)

Date: 12/28/13 Time: 23:06

Sample: 1990 2012

Included observations: 22

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
. * .	. * .	1	0.090	0.090	0.2027	0.653
. .	. .	2	0.037	0.029	0.2384	0.888
. .	. * .	3	-0.056	-0.063	0.3268	0.955
*** .	*** .	4	-0.334	-0.328	3.5913	0.464
. .	. * .	5	0.045	0.114	3.6534	0.600
. ** .	. ** .	6	-0.244	-0.268	5.6238	0.467
. ** .	. ** .	7	-0.194	-0.217	6.9535	0.434
. * .	. * .	8	-0.080	-0.178	7.1951	0.516
. * .	. * .	9	-0.128	-0.124	7.8567	0.549
. * .	. * .	10	0.132	-0.095	8.6255	0.568
. .	. * .	11	0.063	-0.111	8.8151	0.639
. .	. * .	12	0.056	-0.130	8.9823	0.704

Series is stationary for gross capital formation at first difference.

1. OLS Technique

Hypothesis construction:

H₀=insignificant impact (prob>0.1)

H₁=significant impact (prob<0.1)

If coefficients/ dependent variables have significant impact then H₀ will be rejected, otherwise accepted.

Equation 1:

$$DLRGDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 DLREX + \alpha_2 DLGCAP + \alpha_3 DLLABOR + ut$$

Estimation Command:

LS DLRGDP C DLREXPORTS DLGCAP DLLABOR

Table 1:

Variables	Coefficients	Std.Errors	t.Stats	Probability
C	1.644145	0.691874	2.376366	0.0282
DLRGDP	0.033522	0.031525	1.063346	0.3010
DLLABOR	0.953437	0.047734	19.97398	0.0000
DLGCAP	0.254148	0.055127	4.610211	0.0002

R² = 0.996426

Equation 2:

$$DLREXPORTS = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 DLRGDP + \alpha_2 DLGCAP + \alpha_3 DLLABOR + ut$$

Estimation Command:

LS DLREXPORTS C DLREGDP DLGCAP DLLABOR

Table 2:

Variables	Coefficients	Std.Errors	t.Stats	Probability
C	-12.44975	4.783416	-2.602691	0.0175
DLRGDP	1.675577	1.575758	1.063346	0.3010
DLLABOR	-0.788518	1.572469	0.501452	0.6218
DLGCAP	0.308513	0.562868	0.548108	0.5900

$R^2 = 0.892358$

The result based on OLS technique suggests that there is positive relationship between exports and economic growth. But strong effect is from growth to exports and exports to economic growth has smaller role as suggested by empirical results.

As theory suggests that outward oriented policies were adopted by many LDCs that lead to ELG and replaced inward or import substitution policies. But this study gives support to the idea that economic growth itself induces trade flows in Pakistan from 1990-2012.

So it is concluded as well as suggested that both export promotion and import substitution policies may be a good alternative for economic growth and export promotion for Pakistan.

References:

- I. Muhammad.A. Q, Ikram .S and Zahid .A (Winter 2005) An Analysis of Exports and Growth in Pakistan [with Comments] The Pakistan Development Review 44: 4, 921-937
- II. Panayiotis A. R and Dimitris K.C (2005) The export-output growth nexus: Evidence from African and Asian countries 929–940
- III. Nasim S.S and Turkhan A.A.M (Winter 2004) Exports and Economic Growth Nexus: the Case of Pakistan. The Pakistan Development Review 43: 4, 563-581
- IV. Naief A.M (Winter 1993) Exports and Pakistan's Economic Development. Pakistan Economic and Social Review 31:2, 134-146
- V. Azhar .M and Naem. A (Winter 1996) The Export Growth of Pakistan: A Decomposition Analysis.The Pakistan Development Review 35:4 693-702
- VI. Galina .A and Murat F. I (2004) The export skill content, learning by exporting and economic growth Economics Letters 84, 29–34
- VII. Journal of Policy Modeling 26, 165–179 Jacint.B and Manuel C-J (2004) Export composition and Spanish economic growth: evidence from the 20th century. Journal of Policy Modeling 26, 165–179
- VIII. John.T (1997) Exports and economic growth: Evidence from 19th Century Europe. Economics Letters 55, 235–240

- IX. Abdunnasser.H-j (2002) Export performance and Economic growth nexus in Japan:a bootstap approach. Japan and the world economy 14, 25-33
- X. Khalid, M., Mohammed ,N and Muhammad, A.K. (Winter 2004) Volatility of Exchange Rate and Export Growth in Pakistan: The Structure and Interdependence in Regional Markets. The Pakistan Development Review 43: 4, 813-828
- XI. Muhammad, A. A., Rauf, B., Hafeez., Ishrat, B. and Muhammad, M.I. (Winter 2009) A Dynamic Analysis of the Relationship among Human Development, Exports and Economic Growth in Pakistan. The Pakistan Development Review 48: 4, 885-920